

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B143
Date: 1 Dec 2005
Take Off 12:01:26 Cranfield
Landing: 17:02:52 Exeter
Flight Time 5h01m26

Campaign: MICROMIX
Operating Area: SW approaches

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Steve Ball	FAAM
3	3 rd Pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
4	CCM	Sue Angold	Directflight
5	Mission Scientist 1	Clare Lee	Met Office
6	Mission Scientist 2	Jon Taylor	Met Office
7	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
8	Drosondes / CCM2	Doug Anderson	FAAM
9	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office
10	SWS	Ian Rule	Met Office
11	SWS Training	Dave Kindred	Met Office
12	MARSS/DEIMOS	Chawn Harlow	Met Office
13	CPI	Ian Crawford	Manchester University
14	TAFTS	Jon Murray	Imperial College, London
15	Mission Scientist training	Anthony Baran	Met Office
16	SA Obs	Fiona Hilton	Met Office
17			
18			
19			

Flight Track:

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b143
 Date: 1 Dec 2005
 Project: MICROMIX
 Location: SW approaches

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
----	----	-----	-----	---	-----
113044		inu to nav	0.82 kft	126	
114810		engine 1 start	0.83 kft	126	
115451		taxy start	0.83 kft	126	
120126		T/O	0.82 kft	210	from Cranfield
120734		asp open	8.4 kft	327	
121632		jw nevz zero	9.0 kft	254	
124936	132058	Profile 1	22.0 kft	258	
125639		Profile 1	16.0 kft	260	interrupt
125739		Profile 1	16.0 kft	217	resume
130907		Profile 1	5.7 kft	216	500ft/min
131057		Profile 1	4.8 kft	215	interrupt
131209		Profile 1	4.9 kft	120	resume
131743		Profile 1	1.8 kft	118	interrupt
131922		Profile 1	1.8 - 0.83 kft	295	resume
132111	133105	Run 1	0.90 - 0.94 kft	296	100ft
133455	134401	Run 2.1	1.8 kft	114	1000ft
134629	135622	Run 2.2	0.00 kft	293	1000 ft
135759	140312	Profile 2	0.00 kft	115	
140313	141311	Run 3.1	0.00 - 4.6 kft	111	
141454	142446	Run 3.2	4.6 kft	293	
142253		nevz zero	4.6 kft	294	
142625	143148	Profile 3	4.6 - 10.0 kft	113	
143149	144143	Run 4.1	10.0 kft	115	
143528		change tapes	10.0 kft	114	
144332	151553	Profile 4	10.0 - 34.0 kft	300	
150004		Profile 4	26.0 kft	295	interrupt
150215		Profile 4	26.0 kft	148	resume
150351		contrailing	27.4 kft	145	
150615		ufc changed to rfc	29.5 kft	144	for contrails
151345		ge max cool	33.2 kft	145	
151823	152822	Profile 5	34.1 - 25.0 kft	331	
152659		contrails stopped	26.5 kft	327	
153038	154038	Run 5.1	25.1 - 25.0 kft	148	
154243	155009	Run 5.2	25.0 kft	325	
154514		video change	25.0 kft	325	around 5mins ago
155528	155742	Orbit 1	24.0 kft	217	45 deg
155743	155822	Orbit 2	24.0 kft	350	60 deg
155848	160026	Orbit 3	24.1 - 24.0 kft	026	50 deg
160444	161344	Profile 6	24.1 - 32.0 kft	177	
160925		contrailing	28.6 kft	174	
161400	161732	Profile 7	32.0 - 29.0 kft	174	
161943	162944	Run 6	29.1 - 29.0 kft	002	
163209	163713	Profile 8	29.0 - 25.0 kft	177	
163503		contrails stop??	26.6 kft	174	hard to see - getting dark
164507		asp closed	13.7 kft	115	
170252		Land	0.85 kft	255	at exeter
171458		standstill	0.88 kft	140	50'43.93N, 3'24.81W

B143 Track 01-DEC-05

1335 dech. Street brief: 01392 885597
1344 dech with Robin

Trials Instruction for Meteorological Research Flying

Sortie Brief

MICROMIX

Flight: B143

Date: 01 December 2005

Trial Objectives:

To characterise the microphysics of mixed phase cloud and atmospheric state in conjunction with an AMSU overpass for validating radiative transfer models.

Location:

A region of mixed phase cloud anticipated to lie in the South West Approaches which will coincide with an AMSU overpasses at 13:41, 13:54 and 15:23.

Weather:

'Reasonably' homogenous mixed phase cloud.

Flight Pattern:

1. 12:00 Take off Cranfield and transit to operating area at appropriate level (40 mins)
2. 12:40 Profile descent to minimum permitted altitude at 1000 ft/min reducing to 500 ft/min as necessary (15 min) FL220
3. 12:55 One 10 min SLR at 100 ft (10 min)
4. 13:05 Profile ascent to 1000ft below cloud base (10 min)
5. 13:15 Two SLRs of 10 min each (20 min)
6. 13:35 Profile Ascent to Freezing level (5 min)
7. 13:40 Two SLRs of 10 min each at the freezing level adjusting height as necessary - satellite overpass (25 min)
8. 14:05 Profile Ascent to 100 ft above cloud tops (10 min)
9. 14:15 Two SLRs of 10 min each (25 min)
10. 14:40 Profile ascent to max altitude (15 mins)
11. 14:55 Two 10 mins SLRs dropping one sonde at the start of each run (20 min)
12. 15:15 Profile descent to min alt at 1000 ft/min reducing to 500 ft/min as necessary with 10 min SLRs to be performed at levels within cloud to be determined by the aircraft scientist (85 min)
13. 16:40 One 10 min SLR at 100 ft (10 min)
14. 16:50 Recover to Exeter (15 min)
15. 17:05 Land Exeter

Runs and profiles to be conducted at 200 KIAS. Items 6 and 7 should be conducted within cloud as much as possible.

Parking on South side.

Weather Briefing

13:30 Test

13:45 Street brief

Mission Scientist's Debrief

Flight B143 1st December 2005.

Jonathan P Taylor.

The aim of this flight was initially to study mixed phase clouds in the South West Approaches.

On arrival in the area at FL220 it was evident that the cloud in the SW was significantly more broken than forecast. Also there was 8/8 thin Ci overhead which was not apparent on the satellite imagery. The clouds were mainly broken Cu but there were some isolated patches of more significant cumulus development which were drizzling. The maximum tops of the cumulus clouds were FL100.

A profile was flown down to 50ft which penetrated one of the larger convective cells. The freezing layer was at 3800ft and there was considerable shower activity below the most active cells. Following the profile a run was flown at 100ft back under the original cell that was penetrated (just off Lands End).

Two runs were then flown at 1000ft with the microwave radiometers looking up through the cloud cells. This was followed by two runs at 3800ft (the freezing level). All these runs penetrated the same cell. A profile was then flown to FL100 to get above the cumulus clouds and a run at this altitude flown.

Following the study of the cumulus clouds it was decided to characterise the cirrus layer overhead. A profile was flown through the cirrus up to FL340. Cirrus tops were at FL315. During this profile TAFTS failed and remained U/S for the remainder of the sortie. Contrails were seen above FL270. After the profile up a further profile down to FL250 a level below the cirrus cloud was flown. Two runs were flown below the cirrus cloud followed by three orbits below the cloud at FL240. During these runs SWS and ARIES looked up through the cirrus layer. A profile through the cirrus was then flown followed by runs within the cirrus layer to characterise the microphysics. By this time the sun was beginning to set so an end to the science was called and the aircraft recovered to Exeter.

Summary

Some interesting mixed phase clouds studied and some useful cirrus measurements made. The mixed phase clouds may be too small spatially to have been seen by AMSU but this should be checked. The cirrus was very thin and consisted of aggregated ice or graupel in very low concentrations. The cirrus could not be seen on the satellite imagery. There were some regions where there was no cloud below the cirrus so it should be interesting to see how AIRS dealt with this case.

S. TAYLOR

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B163**
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Date 1/12/05

Page 1 of 5

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12000					T/O
1207					Problem with weight on wheels switch if not secured means no CW, NEV, TWC
1210					weight on wheels no warning OK.
121609		F090		52.1/1.2	Above 8/8 CuSc below 2/8 Ci above frontal cloud ahead.
1221			236		climbing thru F090 → F220. Exclusion cloud ahead.
1225		F270	251	51.9/2.1W.	Entering upper layer of cl. 8/8 below. wind 18ms / 200deg
1227					TAFS = NO layer signal trying to fix it.
1228					In cl. - Gampol ≈ 600µm max diam 50/litre.
1233		F220	245		T = -36.29°C / Td = 33.17°C wind 32ms / 201°.
					Some large echoes to NW below us 200m range.
124159					Out of upper layer / Hs.
124239		F220			Thin Ci above cloud well below now SW approaches ahead.
124936		F220			Stg Pt 2/8 Ci above some towering Cu.
125639		F2160			Intercept Pt turning South to get to better cl.
125939		F460			Left Pt 1

Aircraft Scientist's Log

S. Tamarin

Flight No **B.143**.....
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Date 1/12/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
130603					Gi washed in field below some tops up to 8200.
1306.					Entering sill 800/1000 columns of ice crystals. Max diam 1000µm
					v. large cell to south
130845		5000ft.			In cloud $T = -3.15/10 = -1.92^\circ$ Freezing layer
131057	P1	4000ft	215	50.6/69.	Intens. Bertha. wind 18kts / 1500ft
	P1	4000ft ↓ 120			Restart Bertha Freezing base is 3800ft $JW \approx 0.4 \text{ g. m}^{-3}$
			119		wind 193 / 14kts
131601	P1				Raining: 1.16°C . ①
131763	P1	1000ft	120	50.4/63	Intens. down -985mb.
	P1	1000ft ↓ 290			Start big down to 3000ft.
		500ft.			wind 14kts / 1600ft $T = 7.8^\circ\text{C}$ End of P1
132111	R1	1000ft	295	50.5/65.	St of R1. heading back into cell
1322					Raining.
133105	R1	1000ft			End of R1
133455	R2.1	1000ft	114	50.8/7.0W	St of R2.1 ldy E towards large precip. cell.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

J. Tazawa

Flight No **B**.....143.....
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Date 11/2/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					on phone to street.
					End R2.2
					Step P2.2 to freezing level.
140618	R3.1	3800ft			Running in freezing layer. Ps = 980mb
	R3.1	3800ft	110	50.9/60	Passed through another active cell. 7/8 thin Ci overhead. Below Cu below
141311	R3.1				End of R3.1
141454	R3.2	3800ft	293	50.6/5.8	Step R3.2 to freezing level on 980mb.
					passed thro 2 small cells looks like we will miss largest cell. Tops appear lower now.
141904					Going under some thick Cu base now below the cell. Under Cu below.
142302					7/8 Ci at 4/8 Cu/As above
142406	R3.2	3800ft		50.9/6.8	End R3.2
142625	P3	3800ft	116	51/6.6	Step P3 ↑ @ 1000ft/min.
143109	R4.1	F4100	115°		R4.1 Extreme Ci above.
144143	R6.1	F4100		50.9/5.2	End R4.1 and 18kt/21deg
144332	P4	F4100↑	298	50.9/5.2	Step P4 to max alt @ 1000ft/min. Cu looks shallower now extreme Ci above. 7/8 Cu below

Aircraft Scientist's Log

J. TAYLOR

Flight No **B.143**
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Date 1/12/05

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1448	P4	FL260 FL185	296		Probing: wind 12 m/s 225° T = -20 Td = -31
					TAPS 5 u/s no layer present
150000	P0	FL260			Intercept
150215	P4	FL260↑	148	51.3/6.8	Recommence P4 40 litre 200µm sampler.
150330		FL270			Contacting: 96.1 MANSET. 93.1 N1 727 TGT 89.6 N2 6.1 FF/FU
					Ci tops ~ FL315 O ₃ = 112 ppb. T = -58.9°C Td = -53.26°C wind 26 m/s 200 deg
151553	P4↑	FL300	145	50.3/5.5	End of P4 still contacting.
151823	P5↓	FL300	331	50.5/5.3W	Start P5 descent Cto Ci Ci tops slightly lower here x FL300. Low clouds 300-400µm aggregates.
		FL265			Contacting stopped 96.1 MANSET. 62.6 N 523 TGT. 76.3 N2 2.5 FF/FU
152022	P5	FL250		51.3/60	End of P5
153038	P5-1	FL260			ST5-1 O ₃ = 47.15

NW F230
SE
F2250

Aircraft Scientist's Log

J. Taylor

Flight No **B143**.....
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Date 1/12/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
153711					Enter base of Ci at the end of run
154038	R5-1	F2250		50.9/5.2	End run turning on reciprocal to get back under more uniform Ci. clear optical phenomena in Ci
154243	R5-2	F2250	325	50.9/5.3	st Run 5-2 below Ci
154516	R5-2	F2250	325	50.8/5.5	In Ci again at F2250
155009	R5-2	F2250			End R5-2 descended to F2260.
155528	01	F2260			stz obs. 1005°
160026	03				End of obs. P6 gone at 60°
160444	P6↑	F2260	178	51.5/5.7	stz P6↑ complete at 50° θ = 89°.
		F2260			In Ci 100/1000 250µm
160916		F2285			New calculation 93.2 M 726 TGT. 89.3 NZ 6.0 FF/FA.
		F230			clear mostly Ci
161366	P6↑	F2320	179		End of P6
161400	P7↓	F2320	178	50.7/5.4	start of P7 ↓ to level within Ci.
161732	P7	F2290	178		End of P7 wind 30m/s 20deg τ = -56Td = 53.
161903	R6	F2290	0	50.6/5.1w	stz R6 in cumulus. 200µm 50/1000 ~ 100µm
162966	R6	F2290	355		End of R6 mainly below cloud
163209	P8↓	F2290↓		51.6/5.2	stz P8↓ time loss 33m / 2120kg

163713 P8 F2250 178 51.2/5.2 End of P8

END OF SCIENCE

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist 2
C. Lee

Flight No **B.143**
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Date **11/12/05**

Page **1** of **6**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:01:00					T/O.
		FL 90			Transiting thro' Davenport corridor.
					W below. clear above
12:20:44					Climbing to FL220 into operating area.
12:28:07		FL200			2D showing graupel ~ 600µm 5012.
				51.7N, 28W	CPI showing 2mm crystals.
	See Fiona Hilton's notes.				
13:34:50					Heimann cal seems to be underreading by 0.5k.
13:34:55	R2.1	1000ft.			Out of cloud banding towards isolated W cell ahead.
13:39:51					below main cloud base. puffy above.
13:34:53					Heimann still reading reading about 0.5k low.
13:44:51	R2.1	1000ft.			Call to street weather brief
13:46:23	R2.2	1000ft.			
13:49:50					In precip. low values on 2D
13:56:22	R2.2a	1000ft.			Climbing to FL3.8 (ID'd as freezing level)
13:57:59	P2	1000ft.		50.97, 714	Profile ascent.
13:59:43					Hazy above + below

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist 2

Flight No **B.143**

Date 1/12/10

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
140317					In cloud.
140312	P2 end	3800ft.			N.B. Horiz display showing 0 kft.
	R3.1st	3800ft.			
140413					Really in cloud T-0.3
140505					Out of cloud.
140831			110		cloud above.
140922					2D showing some particles.
					N.B. Press height reading incorrectly (4.6kft based on ground P of 1013kft.)
141318	R3.1st				End of run at freezing level.
141407					In cloud.
141459			296		Above cloud.
141454	R3.2st	3800ft.	100		Reciprocal on.
141740					wind 8ms ⁻¹ / 169°
					Over cloud.
141833					clear above/below slightly hazy
142446	R3.2nd				Right turn.
142625	P3st	3800ft.	115	51.0, 6.7W	Profile climb.
142706					In cloud some turbulence.
142741					precip on VFC.
142859					clear above, 3/4 W below.
143130					6 above, hazy below.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist 2.

Flight No **B.143**.....

Date **1/12/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14:31:48	P3 end				
	R4.1	FL100			ci above, patchy w below.
14:35:48			114		Above w, thin ci above T _e = -9.1°C, T _D = -19.97°C
	R4.1 end				
14:47:32	P4 st				
15:05					Contrailing. - v. large + thick. video has been changed to capture them.
		FL300			In ci, 2D seeing CPL just seeing wisps.
15:08:55		FL310			2D still seeing small concs. SID 1 < 100 particles/sec.
15:10:30		FL315			At top of ci?
15:11:32		FL320	145		SID showing clear - no particles still contrailing wind 25 m/s @ 205°
					Can clearly see through ci, patchy w below.
15:55:53	P4 end	FL340			ci, various thicknesses but all T less than 1
					turning left
15:18:23	P5 st	FL340	332		descent thro' ci down to FL250.

Aircraft Scientist's Log Mission Scientist 2

 Flight No **B.143**

 Date **1/12/05**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					SWS viewing up with 6° compensation for true zenith.
152248					2D seeing low concs. 100/l. CPI low concs 300 → 400µm aggregates (no positive crystals).
152628					patchy w below. thin Ci above $\tau < 1^a$
152650		FL263	327	51.2, 5.9	Con trails stopped.
152822	P5.1st	FL250			profile end turning left.
153038	R5.1st	FL250	149	51.3 16.1	Straight + level on below Ci. v. patchy w below.
153150					2D still picking up low concs.
153210					Seeing hazy patch on DFC. SWS seeing increase in signal due to Ci
153510					UAE - thicker Ci 3/8 w below.
153640					2D concs. increased to 100/l. Some hazy patches below + 2/8 w → 3/8
154243	R5.2st	FL250	327		Reciprocal on to get back to sheet of Ci + ready to do abits below.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist 2

Flight No **B143**.....

Date **1/12/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
				w.b.	At end of R5.1 could see optical phenomena from Li at of right right window. During right turn could see it in FFC.
154659					CP1 seeing some large ice 2D seeing ice. no contrails.
1550 ⁰⁹ 13	R5.2nd	FL250 FL240	327		CP1 100/8' 125 → 250µm descending to definitely get below Li (not noted as a profile) straight + level for short time.
155328	01	FL240			Orbit 1 to left at 45° Li looking thin above.
155714	0end		110		3/8 → 4/8 W below.
155746	02.		020		Orbit 2. at 60°
155848	03		030		couldn't maintain angle. Orbit 3 at 50°
					En very low on base horizon.
160027	03end		358		ascent need to get back to FL240. profile ascent.
160444	P6.1st	FL240			to get into cloud. upto FL320
160930		FL286	174		contrails
					2D 55 → 60 / L 25µm
					CP1 low conc.

T_f = 54.0, T_D = 50.5

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Mission Scientist 2

Flight No **B.143**

Date **12/1/05**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
161240					contacts thickening
					OB = 90pp.
161344	P6 end	FL320			profile
					profile descent. to
161400	P7 st.	FL320			get back into cloud.
161732	P7 end.	FL290.			end of profile
	R	FL290			left turn.
161943	R6 st.	FL290	0	50.6/5.1	T ₁ = -52.8, T ₂ = -52.05
					In cloud. Ci
					2D 50/1L 150µm (small)
					CPI low concs.
					Still contracting.
162606					2D v. low concs. 3/1L.
					thick w. below ~ 718
					maybe in the bottom of cloud.
162944	R6 end	FL290.			turning left.
163209	P8 st.	FL290			descent. back through cloud.
					hazy above, 718w below,
					in very low
					difficult to see contrails
163730	P8 end	FL250			Profile finished. Transit to
					Exeter
					ARIES OK (1 small glitch in hot BB)
					TAFS no laser fringes
					MARS OK. Demos some probs before

~17:00

landing Exeter.

SWS OK.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Fiona Hutton

Flight No **B.143**.....

Date01/12/05.....

Page ...1... of ...8...

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12.28.36		FL200			low upper level cloud ^{20%} grouped up to 600µm 50/L; v large on CPI
					Lower level cloud extensive Cu around 1900ft
12.33.55		FL220			just entered cloud again
12.39					plot shows we're just passing over coast. still thick cloud below
12.42.29					Now completely over the sea, now emerged from cloud @ FL220
12.44.38		FL220			cumulus below thinning out and becoming more patchy
12.47.41		FL220			entering thin cirrus - large ice CPI pretty much clear below - just small convective cumulus below
12.49.36	P1	FL220			Descent to surface with possible interrupt
12.51.27		20400			thin patchy cirrus ^{below} and below that thin patchy cumulus.
12.56.39	Interrupt P1	FL160			Interrupt for heading change
12.57.39	Recomm	FL160			recommencing descent. Currently clear air below, thin cirrus above
13.06.13		8400			entering cloud
					DP -6.75 T -6.88
13.08.00					cloud slightly intermittent below
		8400			Change rate of descent

Aircraft Scientist's Log

NB Flight manager's times usually seem up to 5 secs off

Flight No **B**.....143.....

Date01/12/05.....

Page2 of 8.....

FAAM © 2004

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13.10.10					cloud free below & above
13.10.57	P1 inter	4800			Interrupt profile to change angle
13.12.00	P1 rec.	4800			beginning again
13.12.52	inter	4800			precipitation
13.13.51		3900			precipitation
					20: mixed particles part-melted
					xals & large water droplets.
13.15.1					T.1.3C
13.15.00					now exiting cloud.
13.17.42	inter	1000			interrupted profile to turn back
					round.
13.19.23	recomm	1000			profile descent to 50ft
13.20.08					within cloud above,
13.20.58	P1	100ft			End of profile
13.21.11	R1	100ft			Begin of Run 1 in
13.23.00					In precip for 1st 1/2,
13.31.05	End R1	100ft			End Run 1
13.33.05	P2	100ft			profile to 1000ft
					FI Man - heimann to low 0.5k
13.34.45	P2 end	1000ft			
13.34.55	R2-1	1000ft			reasonably clear, thin cirrus
					above
13.39.53					just below cloud base now Cu.
13.41.15					droplets 800-1000um droplets -
					just small amount.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.143**.....

 Date**01.12.05**.....

 Page **3** of **8**..

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
13.43.30					clear again
					Heinmann underreading 0.4°C
					SST 10.25
13.44.46	R2.1 end	1000 ft			
13.46.23	R2.2	1000 ft			skull mostly clear thin cirrus
13.49.26					cloud above thickening patchily
13.49.54					precipitation (slight)
13.56.23	R2 end				climb to 3800
13.58.01	P3 "P2"	1000 ft			climb to 3800
					→ NB flight manager didn't record previous profile so he's calling this "P2"
14.03.11	P2 end	3800			+ enter cloud
14.03.23	R3				exit cloud
14.03.23	R3.1	3800			exit cloud
14.04.04					enter cloud, height data back
				INTRACE	T - 0.1 DP 1.11
14.05.00				height is	clear
14.06.20				4600	just below cloud t = 0.0 DP 0.0
14.08.58				Press 855mb	grazing base of cloud -
14.11.53					grazing cloud again
14.13.12	R3.1 end	3800			
14.14.46	R3.2	3800			in cloud immediately
					then then straight out into
					patchy cirrus.

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.143**.....

 Date **01/12/05**.....

 Page **4** of **8**

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
14.16.59	R3.2	3800			entering clear patch again
14.17.27					patchy cumulus below, mostly clear above
14.18.50					
14.18.50					new cloud above, clear below
14.20					only thin cirrus above
14.23.50					slightly thicker cloud above now,
14.24.48	R3.2 END	3800			End of Run
14.26.27	"P3"	3800			to FL100
14.27.02					entering cumulus
14.27.35		~4800?			exit cumulus
14.31.43	P3 end	FL100			
14.31.43	R4	FL100			cirrus above, some cu below
↳	R4 end				
14.42.30					
14.43.32	P4	FL100			climb to FL350
					cirrus above, patchy, small cumulus below
15.00.04	interrupt	FL260			Interrupt profile
15.02.17	Recom	FL260			climb to FL350
15.03.03					2D small conc ^{graupel} up to 200µm 40/l
					CPI = noise
15.03.30					containing T - 49.66 DP - 47.03
15.04.52					CPI = noise
					2D <100/l 75-150µm
15.06.09					2D 50µm

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.143**.....

Date01/12/05.....

Page ...5 of 8...

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
15.06.30					CPI large ice but v few particles
15.07.56		30400			just in base of cirrus
					Still contrailing
					SID v small conc 100/sec
15.09.46		31200			Exiting cirrus? SID - 100/sec
15.10.20		81500			top of cirrus
15.11.30		32200			SID clear - cirrus & small ch below
					Still monster contrails
15.13.12					T = -59.14 DP -53.39
15.15.55	P4end	FL340			end of profile
15.18.23	P5	FL340			descent to FL250
15.21.13		31400			CI now v thin below here,
					small ch
15.22.10					SID SID doesn't see much, but
					is getting v low count 10/sec
15.22.50					SID: low conc 100/mm
					CPI: low conc 3-400/mm agg
15.24.48					Still looks hazy outside the'
					T = -51.46, DP = -54.49
15.26.12					contrails dissipating
					T = -48.59, DP -51.7
15.26.43	P5	26500			contrails stopped F -47.8 DP -51.1
15.28					now below cirrus
15.28.22	P5 end	FL250			End of profile

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.153**
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Date **1/12/05**

Page **6** of **8**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
15.29.24					cirrus above patches of cu below
15.30.40	R51	FL250			ci above, cu below
					2D low conc ice crystals
15.36.20					2D 100/L
15.37.05					now hazy cloud below as well as the cu, still cirrus above
15.37.45					seem to be exiting edge of ci - much clearer
15.38.00					can see contrails from previous run above & to left persisting
15.42.43	R5.2	FL250			ci v thin above us
15.46.27					ci seems to be thickening to the left - sun is not really getting through them, sun low
					no contrails
15.47.00					CPI large ice
15.48.40					^{rim} 100/L & 225-250 μm
					cloud base dropping
15.50.11	R5.2 end	FL250			Run 5.2 end
					Descent 1000 ft
15.51.23					now seem to be below cirrus
15.52		FL240			
15.55.25	orbit start (ish)				45° orbits 2
					Turn to left looks steeper than
15.57.13	orbit end				45° from front / near camera
15.57.39	(02)		020		started 60°
15.58.50	(03)	240	030		50°
16.00.27	03 end				

Aircraft Scientist's Log

 Flight No **B.143**.....

 Date **1/12/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Sun v low
16.04.45	P6	FL240			climb to FL 310+
					cloud conditions still the same
16.06.27					seem to be entering cirrus
					LD 100/L 250µm
16.08.38					T = -50.89 DP = -47.73
16.09.07		28300			Contrails
					LD 55-60/L 25µm
					CPI v low conc
16.12.36		31200			looks like we're coming out of Ci now
16.13.46	P6 end	32000			End of Ascent
16.14.02	P7	32000			Descent
16.15.04					"Quadruple contrail"!
16.15.36					Back to normal contrails
16.16.59		29400			entering ci
					T = -53.3 DP = -53.4ish
16.17.34	P7 end	29000			
16.19.43	R6	29000			
16.20.31					LD 50/L 150µm
					CPI similar
16.26.00					LD 3/L
16.29.44	P6 end	29000			
16.32.10	P8	29000			Descent to 25000
					Ci below now thick ^{more even} coverage
					can't tell if still contrailing

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.143**.....

Date **11/12/05**.....

Page **1** of **2**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1200					TO
1228					Very large aggregates Very few irregular structures. up to ~ 1 um in size plate-aggregates
1235					Mixed Plate conditions Very large plate-aggregates, water spheres.
					Very different to B142 with more plate-like columns and plates but fewer plate aggregates associated with B142 sizes ~ 1 um in size
					Suggestion B143 more plate-like B142 with aggregates
1249					More grouped like columns & large clus
1078					Mixed Plate conditions Grouped + aggregates 3 columns stuck together long needles

Aircraft Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.143**
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Date **4/24/05**

Page **2** of **2**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
150		Meap			Obstacles w/ hood - base
203	run	3800ft			run 3.1 1403 12 sec
206					In cloud results, obs + water phase
208					water phase
214	2nd run	passing level		3800ft	
227	Passing level	run			water phase significant conc extinction.
1502	profile up to	3500ft			AI noise
1506	CPI	Some		6000ft	measured ~ 100 m ² class per concentration for liquid phase
31,000ft	3-10pm		NO		L ¹ ~ 3400ft
1518	3400ft	profile	some		
1521					RETURN AND collect irregulars of low conc
Profile	5000ft				clouds dominated by irregulars No particle hexagonal structures recorded.
1524					Some data 12000ft
347					CPI Records large irregulars
351					obs. 73! 45° complete 60° partial 50° complete

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date: 1/12/05	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 10:38:45	DAU1 Time: + 0	DAU2 Time: + 1	DAU3 Time: +1	Aux1 Time: + 0	Aux2 Time:	Page 1 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
12:39:45	Noise		221					Noise								Start Profile 1 from FL220	
12:50:49	Noise							Noise								FL210	
12:51:50	Noise							Noise								FL200	
12:52:59	Noise							Noise								FL190	
12:54:03	Noise															FL180	
12:55:19	Noise							Noise								FL170	
12:56:36	Noise															FL160	
12:58:50	Noise															FL150	
12:59:50	Noise															FL140	
13:00:53	Noise															FL130	
13:01:54	15	0.06		1												FL120	
13:03:03	15	0.06		1												FL110	
13:04:20	5	0.06		1												FL100	
13:05:29	20	0.06		100		65	800									FL090	
13:06:30	300	0.11		1000		500	800	20000	1000						6	FL080	
13:07:30	50	0.12		50		5	800								6	FL070	
13:08:45	200	0.20	241	1000		15	75								12	FL060	
13:10:47	35	0.09		10												FL050	
13:13:47	125	0.10	248	1000		20	800	8000	1800							FL040	
13:15:40	70	0.08	257	10												FL030	
13:17:20	45	0.08		20												FL020	
13:20:56	70	0.08		20												End of Profile 1 @ 50'	
13:21:06																Start Run 1 @ 100'	
13:22:00	75	0.08		50		1	800	430	3000	0.02					1		
13:24:00	55	0.08	259	30		1											
13:26:00	60	0.08		20													
13:28:00	65	0.08		20													
13:30:00	75	0.08		15													
13:31:06																End of Run 1	
13:33:03	80	0.07		10												Start Profile 2.1 from 100'	
13:34:44	70	0.07		10												End of Profile 2.1 & Start Run 2.1 @ 1000'	
13:35:00	80	0.07		10													
13:37:00	65	0.07		5													
13:39:00	55	0.07		20													
13:41:00	50	0.07	262	100		20	800	2000	1000	0.02					1		
13:43:00	60	0.07		20													
13:44:45																End of Run 2.1	
13:46:22																Start of Run 2.2 @ 1000'	
13:47:00	85	0.07		5													
13:49:00	70	0.07	263	10													
13:51:00	85	0.07	264	20		10	800	2000	1800	0.02					1		
13:53:00	80	0.07		20													
13:55:00	75	0.07		10													
13:56:25																End of Run 2.3	
13:58:01	90	0.07		10												Start Profile 2.2 from 1000'	
14:03:13																End of Profile 2.2 Start Run 3.1 @ 3800'	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date: 1/12/05	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 10:38:45	DAU1 Time: + 0	DAU2 Time: + 1	DAU3 Time: +1	Aux1 Time: + 0	Aux2 Time:	Page 2 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
14:04:00	85	0.06	294	10													
14:06:00	40	0.07		10													
14:08:00	60	0.08		10		40	800	4000	800	0.03					6		
14:10:00	110	0.08	296	5													
14:12:00	35	0.07		5													
14:13:11																End of Run 3.1	
14:14:45																Start Run 3.2 @ 3800'	
14:15:00	40	0.07	313	1000		30	200								12		
14:17:00	80	0.07	314	10													
14:19:00	80	0.08		10													
14:21:00	65	0.08		10													
14:23:00	65	0.08		10													
14:24:46																End of Run 3.2	
14:26:25	45	0.07								Error						Start Profile 3 from 3800'	
14:28:00	25	0.07	358	10												FL060	
14:29:01	20	0.07		5												FL070	
14:30:02	6	0.07		2												FL080	
14:30:48	9	0.07		1												FL090	
14:31:42	9	0.07														End of Profile 3 @ FL100	
14:32:00	5	0.07															
14:34:00	10	0.06															
14:36:00	5	0.06		1													
14:38:00	8	0.06															
14:40:00	40	0.06															
14:41:43																End of Profile 3	
14:43:32	5	0.06														Start Profile 4 from FL100	
14:44:37	6	0.06		1												FL110	
14:45:45	3	0.06		1												FL120	
14:46:40	6	0.06														FL130	
14:47:45	8	0.06														FL140	
14:48:48	8	0.06														FL150	
14:49:42	8	0.06														FL160	
14:50:49	2	0.06														FL170	
14:51:41	8	0.06														FL180	
14:52:38	10	0.06														FL190	
14:53:39	35	0.06														FL200	
14:54:45	Noise															FL210	
14:55:44	Noise															FL220	
14:56:52	Noise															FL230	
14:57:59	Noise															FL240	
14:58:58	Noise															FL250	
15:00:08	Noise			5		10	150	Noise							10	FL260 Rearm 2 1	
15:01:00																Logging problems	
15:07:40			361	100		2	25	Noise							11	FL300	
15:09:42	Noise		362	100		Noise		Noise								FL310	
15:11:10	Noise			1		Noise		Noise								FL320	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B

Date: 1/12/05	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 10:38:45	DAU1 Time: + 0	DAU2 Time: + 1	DAU3 Time: +1	Aux1 Time: + 0	Aux2 Time:	Page 3 of 4
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		2D2-P		CIP25			CIP100			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Max size	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Max size	LWC		
15:13:27	Noise		362	1		Noise		Noise								FL330	
15:15:52	Noise					Noise		Noise								End of Profile 4 @FL340	
15:18:23	Noise			1		Noise		Noise								Start Profile 5 from FL340	
15:19:30	Noise			1		Noise		Noise								FL330	
15:20:39	Noise			5				Noise								FL320	
15:21:41	Noise			10		3	100	Noise							10	FL310	
15:23:00	Noise			10		8	175	Noise							10	FL300	
15:24:00	Noise		363	50		20	125	Noise							11	FL290	
15:25:04	Noise			100		45	150	Noise							10	FL280	
15:26:16	Noise			2		3		Noise								FL270	
15:27:26	Noise			5		1		Noise								FL260	
15:28:23	Noise			2				Noise								End of Profile 5 @ FL250	
15:30:38																Start Run 5.1 @ FL250	
15:31:00	Noise			10		10	150	Noise							10		
15:33:00	Noise			20		6	175	Noise							10		
15:35:00	Noise			80		55	225	Noise							10		
15:37:00	Noise		364	150		80	150	Noise							10		
15:39:00	Noise							Noise									
15:40:39																End of Run 5.1	
15:42:41																Start Run 5.2 @ FL250	
15:43:00	Noise							Noise									
15:45:00	Noise			5		1		Noise									
15:47:00	Noise		365	100		100	200	Noise		0.01							
15:49:00	Noise		367	100		70	275	Noise		0.01					10		
15:50:10																End of Run	
15:55:25																Start of Orbits @ FL240	
16:00:26																End of Orbits	
16:04:45	Noise			10		3	175	Noise							10	Start Profile 6 from FL 240	
16:05:42	Noise			50		30	175	Noise							10	FL250	
16:06:50	Noise		368	90		50	250	Noise		0.01					10	FL260	
16:08:04	Noise		369	90		40	175	Noise							10	FL270	
16:09:00	Noise			80		25	150	Noise							10	FL280	
16:10:10	Noise			90		20	100	Noise							11	FL290	
16:11:11	Noise		370	80		40	150	Noise							10	FL300	
16:12:15	Noise			150		65	100	Noise							11	FL310	
16:13:45	Noise		370	1												End of profile 6 & Start Profile 7 @ FL320	
16:15:25	Noise			5		6	100	Noise							11	FL310	
16:16:31	Noise		371	30		15	175	Noise							10	FL300	
16:17:29	Noise			100		70	175	Noise							10	End of Profile 7 @ FL290	
16:19:44																Start Run 6 @ FL290	
16:20:00	Noise		372	100		50	150	Noise							10		
16:22:00	Noise			200		90	175	Noise							10		
16:24:00	Noise		373	90		25	175	Noise							10		
16:26:00	Noise		374	5		2	150	Noise							10		
16:28:00	Noise			3		1		Noise									
16:29:44																End of Run 6	

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B143

Date: 01/12/2005

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC B143_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B143_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	21/12/05	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: B143 b) Path name: MFDDATA:B143_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	21/12/05	
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: B143 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	n 21/12/05	Note the calibration file used FFSSP_CAL19112005.TXT Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour complete
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B143_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:B143_mfdX','pmsdata:B143_m5procffssp',auto=602 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit		Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto Auto-correct with Nevzorov LWC 3 sec added to FFSSP time
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B143_m5procffssp b) Datset: mfddata:B143_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	21/12/05	
7) CHECKS:		
i) FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC – are they correctly synchronized in time?		Looks OK. FFSSP in good agreement with Nevz LWC
ii) If not, may be necessary to repeat 5b) using addt=x keyword. This adds x sec to FFSSP time.		

Preparation of imagery for Core data product		
iii) WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B143 c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10 iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	120126 164800 10 PMSDATA:	2DC noise 150900-151900 2DP noise 124200-125400 142700-164747 FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_B143_2Dx-IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files		
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO		
a) Flight number: B143 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B143_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: 0 if unknown i) End time: 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:B143_PROC2D	0 120126 162730 162708 164800 0.2 8 / 8 2 21/12/05	If program crashes at a certain Time, for any reason, re-run With that time as the new end. Crash at 162708 Note the particle type Bnnn_PROC2D_1 and .._2 Output files generated
10) In PVWAVE		
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:B143_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:B143_M5PROC2D' iii) exit	21/12/05	Each PROC2D file done separately
11) MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B143_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:B143_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		
12) CHECKS:		
i) Is 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC?		OK in ice cloud regions

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	01/12/05	Flight	B143	log pages
Operator(s)	Harlow		Campaign	MICROMIX		
Departure	Cranfield		Arrival	Cranfield		

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection	X	
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers	X	
Close all MARSS circuit breakers	X	
FERA on	at time 10:40	
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16 54°C	Ch 58°C Ch18 40°C
Temperature controller set points	54°C	17 58 °C -20 40°C
MARSS CPU on	at time 10:40	
Initial target temperatures	Hot 343	Cold 283
Target heating	X	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***	X	
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time 10:40	
Scan indication	Monitor x	Visual X

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers	X	
Turn on Deimos CPU		
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***		
Start Deimos Software	at time 10:40	
Initial target temperatures	Hot	Cold
Target heating		
Scan indication	Monitor	Visual
Weather	Cloud Low + at 8/8	Precip light
	Surface Yes	Pressure
	Other	

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$		at time	
Brightness temps 'sensible'	X			
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot 344.56	Cold 278.62	
	Deimos:	Hot	Cold	
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A (-)	Ch3 A (-)	Ch1 B (-)	Ch3 B (-)
	Ch16 (40-44) 1.	Ch17 (45-49) 35.	Ch18 (40-44) 37.5	Ch19 (40-44) 37.45
			Ch20 (44-48) 40.57	

Power changeover

Headset on before start	
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)	
Exit Deimos Software (x)	
POWER CHANGEOVER	
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton
Restart Deimos Software	
System running again	at time

ARIES flight log

Flight: B143

Location: SW approaches

page 1 of 4

Date: 1-12-5

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes: Micromic

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
095855	preflight	B143B	C	42	23	14	-189.9	17.2	CH1x1	
110059	"	B143C	C	71.2	30.4	14.3	-190.0	22.1	"	
114949	E/ start	B143D	C	71	31	17	-190	25.5	—	
1202	T/O									
120821	Transit FL90	B143D	C	71	31	14.5	-189.9	25.9	CH1x2	1/8 Sca ↓ 1/8 ↑ entering darker con.
121029	" FL90	B143E	O	70	31	12.8	-190	26	Z1x5	fairly clear overhead except
1212	Turn to port									many persistent contrails
121610	FL90, turn	B143F	C	71	31	9.1	-190	21.8	CH1x2	Tornado 9 o'clock 2 miles
121855	"	B143G	C						N1x5	
122058	climb to 220	"	C	71	31	8.6	-189.9	21.3		
122359	"	B143H	C	71	31	7.6	-189.9	21.6	CH1x2	1/8 ↓ 1/8 ↑ thickening
122552	Transit	B143I	C	71	31	5.8	-190	20.6	N1x5	entering cloud at 1228 about
122850	"									about
123042	"	B143J	C	71	31	4.1	-189.9	20.7	CH2x2	in cloud top
125512	PI, R16	B143K	C	71	31	-8.6	-189.9	18.1	CH2x3	fair bit of thin C ↑, 1/4 white just below, 50 CH ↓
132100	EP1/SR1	B143L	C	71	31	-4.3	-190	15.9	CH1x2	70' - 100'
132307	R1 (100')	B143M	C	71	30	6.3	-190	17.7	N1x2	intermittent precip
132507	R1	B143N	C	71	31	7.8	-190	15.7	CH1x1	
132826	"	B143O	C	71	31	8.2	-190	16	N1x4	dry

ARIES flight log

Flight: B143

Location: SW approaches

page 2 of 4

Date: 1-12-05

Operator(s): VANCE

Resolution: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes:

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Sshr	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
133008	R1	B143P	C	71	31	10.2	-190	15	CH1x2	133105, ER1 - in 2nd cal.
133447	R2(1000')	B143Q	C	71	31	11.6	-190	16	CHx1	
133558	"	B143R	O	70	31	12	-190	17	Z1x1	
133704	"	B143S	O	71	30	12	-190	16	Z1x3	
134101	"	B143T	C	71	31	12.8	-190	16	CH1x1	in rain
134214	"	B143U	C	71	31	14.4	-190	16.7	N1x3	in clear. last resenter
134505	ER2.1	B143V	C	71	31	13.3	-190	16.9	CH1x1	in turn (sthd
134657	R2.2	B143W	O	70	30	13.3	-190	16.8	Z1x4	shutter closed in last 3
135105	R2.2	B143X	C	71	31	14	-190	17	CH1x1	well rain band
135214	"	B143Y	C	71	31	14	-190	17	N1x3	clean.
135509	"	B143Z	C	71	30	13.5	-190	17.3	N1x1	"
135626	ER2.2	B143Ø	C	71	31	14.0	-190	17.3	CH1x1	" sthd turn.
135742	sthd turn	B1431	C	71	31	14	-190	17.9	CH1x1	+sthd p2
1408	R3.1(330m)	B1432	C	71	31	11.9	-190.6	17.9	SOFTWARE RESTART. (Precautionary)	
										⚠ this MAY have been B - good! it should be!
142548	R3.2(6)	B1434	O	71	31	9.9	-190.6	9	CH2x1	
143200	R4.1	B1435	C						CH1x1	
143314	R4.1	B1436	O	70	31	7.4	-190.4	16.8	Z1x3	
143755	R4.1	B1437	C	71	31	5.1	-190.6	15.7	CH1x1	

APR 1987
 p → Ch. 2 Pfl below, Zenith
 0017

ARIES flight log

Flight: B143 Location: SW Approaches page 8 of 4

Date: 1-12-5 Operator(s): VANCE Resolution: 1 Gain A: 2 B: 2

Notes: MICROMIX

DRS time	Flight ptrn	Filename	Sht	HBB	CBB	Mir.	Det.	Win	Macro(s)	Comments
143805	R4.1	B1438	0	70	31	4.5	-190.6	15.5	Z1X2	
144240	R4.1	B1439	C	71	31	3.9	-190.6	16.1	CH1X1	
152827	EP5	C143A	C	71	31	-25	-190.6	17.8	CH1X1	FL250 part turn
153044	R5.1	C143B	0	71	30	-25	-190.6	17.3	Z1X4	low conc. ice crystals one missing 1GM in C143B004
153518	R5.1	C143C C143C	C	71	31	-24.6	-190	10.0	CH1X1	FL250
153642	"	C143D C143D	0	70	31	-24.1	-190	+10.4	Z1X4	into cloud, causing one missing
154112	E2	C143E	C	71	31	-23.9	-189.9	10.0	CH1X1	sltd turn FL250
154255	R5.2	C143F	K/O	70	31	-23.7	-189.9	9.8	Z1X2	1st 8 scans W/ sltd C.
154453	R5.2	C143G	0	71	31	-23.6	-189.9	7.7	Z1X1	
154710	R5.2	C143H	C	70	31	-22.6	-189.9	12.5	CH1X1	FL250
154956	R5.2	C143I	C	71	31	-22	-190	15	CH1X1	"
155151	R6.01	C143J	C	71	31	-22	-190	17.8	CH1X1	FL240
155540	O1	C143K	0	71	31	-22	-190	18.2	Z1X1	45°
155640		C143L	0						Z1X1	
155746	O2	C143M	0	60°					Z1X1	80° abouted O, more cont.
155855	O3	C143N	0	71	31	-22	-190	6.1	Z1X1	50° Scan mark 119
150120	E03	C143O	C	71	31	-20	-189.9	13.5	CH1X2	↓

200g.

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 143	Date	1/12/05	Operator(s)	DK (VT); IDL	log page	1 of 6
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	MIRR Pos	Int Times		Remarks	
				Vis	NIR		

← (Test various integr² times) Shutter needed re-setting (x1)

110833				750	1000	Dark Measurement	
110906	Pre-Flt.	—	→ (AFT)	750	1000	FOV 90° AFT; pre-flight testing (Sample period 1.00 sec) (Temp +15°C)	
114604			AFT	750	1000	STOP;	
115200						All Peltiers off (Temp +9°C)	
115500						Start Taxi.	
120128						T/O Cranfield.	
120242						Into cloud	
121006						→ Camera rearing 'out' (LP)	
121127			↑	300	1000	But dir to zenith ↑ Start dark cal.	
121207						Start measurement. (VIS 'clipped' at top)	
121251			↑	350	1000	Start dark cal.	
121321			↑	350	1000	Start measurement.	
121500	Transit	090	↑	350	1000	At FL 090; 8/8 Cu / Sc below 7/8 Thin Ac & 7/8 Ci above (CONTINUES TO PAGE)	
122150						Temp +12.	
122445						Change view to ↓. Nadir (6° pitch taking into acc)	
122803			↓ [*] (-6°)	950	750	Start Dark Cal ² * nadir (-6° AFT)	
122827	Transit	21.0kft	↓ [*] (-6°)	150	750	Start Measurement ✓ OK.	
123133	"		↓ [*]	100	500	Start Dark Cal ² * nadir	
123157	"		↓ [*]	100	500	Start Measurement (-6° AFT)	
123548	"	22.0	↑ [*]	75	500	Start Dark Cal ² ↑ zenith [*]	
36.4m	"	"	↑	30	400	Start Measurement (+6° FOL)	
123659			↑	30	400	Start Measurement	
38.2m						Start Dark Cal.	
123840	Transit	21.9kft	↑	75	400	Start Measurement	
124345	"	22.0kft	↑ [*]	200	1000	Start Dark View (+12°C) [*]	
124414						Start Measurement (As above)	

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 143	Date	1/12/05	Operator(s)	DLK/(U/T); IDL	log page	2	of	6
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

1249			←						Start P1.
125024				150	500				Start Dark Cal
125040	P1 ↓	20.9	↑ *	150	500				Start Measurement (* Pankaj) (Face 6°)
									Ci thicker above at begin P1 ↓.
125639	P1 ↓	16.0	↑ *	150	500				Interrupt P1 to turn. (* 6° Face)
		(Sample Period 1 sec)							
125741									Resume P1 ↓
130807	P1 ↓	6.5 kft	↑ *	150	500				Coming into CL soon. (* 6° Face)
130900		5.7 kft							Changing descent rate → 500'/min
131014									(+D.C.) Clear spot below (500' - CW to side). Ci 'above
131057	P1 ↓	(Horace) 7.5 kft	↑ *	150	500				Interrupt P1 at 4000'. F. level (3700').
131340									Underside layer CW there, pp ⁿ SWS response temporarily higher. Mixed (mainly large water drops). pp ⁿ
		←							
131743	P1	(1000 on 985) 1.7 kft (Horace)	↑ *	150	500				Interrupt P1 & turn with reciprocal (HW)
1319	P1		↑ *	150	500				Resume P1 (to 50') (SWS Temp +12C)
132058	P1 end	(0.8 kft) 50'	↑ *	150	500				End P1. / Start R 100'. R1.
132111									
132300			←						pp ⁿ now - (~20 sec) Vis & IR signals varying a lot on this run. Clipping at top at times; lower signal at other times. Integ r ⁿ times left "9.5 is".
132923									Dark View
132944			↓ *	1000	1000				Measure.
133105	End R1	100'							End R1
133157									Start Dark Cal.
133225		100'	↑ *	150	500				Start Measure Start P2 ↑ 100' to 1000'

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B / 43	Date	1/12/05	Operator(s)	DJK(V/T); JDL	log page	3	of	6
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks			
				Vis	NIR				

		(1.8kft) ¹⁰¹³							
133455	R2.1	1000' (400)	↑*	150	500	Start R at 1000' (+12°C)			
						Start Ci Above (Cu to sides)			
123945			↑*	150	500	Into pp ^{new} under thicker cloud (Cu)			
						(increase in vis signal for 5-10 secs)			
124031						Into pp ^{new}			
4135						(800-1000 μm size droplets here from 2D)			
124454		(1.7kft) ¹⁰¹³	↑*	150	500	End R 2.1			
1246	2.2	1000'	↑*	150	500	Start R2.2			
134750						TIME CHECK GOOD (Hence/SWS)			
						(WITHIN 1 Sec)			
134957						St. pp ^{new} (On Flight Deck)			
						screen			
135048	2.2	1000'	↑*	150	500	Main Run to part, catching edge of it.			
						(12°C - Temp)			
135622	2.2	1000'	↑*	150	500	End R2.2, Turn reciprocal			
						then climb to FL (3800')			
						(Generally thin Ci above only)			
135759	P2	1000'	↑*	150	500	Start P2. (x6 fold)			
140006	P2	Climbing	↑*			Start Deck Cal. (increase			
140026				250	750	Start Measurement now (Integr ^{new} time)			
	End/	(4.6kft) ¹⁰¹³				Hence HEIGHT = 0!			
140312	P2/Start	3800'	↑*	250	750	End P2/Start R3			
		R3-1 (954)							
140446						Start Deck Cal. (IAS spectrum clipped so..)			
140509	R3.1	3800'	↑*	150	500	Start Measurement now (decrease integr ^{new} time)			
						Hence/SWS TIME			
						IS 5% - cloud 50% exactly			
140740						Peltiers R2 on (TEMP = +13)			
140950		(4.6kft) ¹⁰¹³				Good spectra (vis peaking 50k)			
						IR " 10k			
141318	R3.1	3800'	↑*	150	500	End R3.1 Turning & auto loop.			
141454	3.2	3800'	↑*	150	500	START 3.2 (spectra in created sig. for ~ 10 sec at start of run)			

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 143	Date	1/12/05		Operator(s)	JLK (U/T) & IDR		log page	4 of 6		
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks					
				Vis	NIR						

142446	3.2	3800'	↑*	150	500	End L3.2	(* Zenith +6° FOLIE)				
							(SWS Temp = +12°C)				
142625	P3	3800'	↑*	150	500	Start P3					
142715							} into cloud & still turb.				
							} (spectra peaking now vis up to 65k) for IR ~ 20k) (from 15000)				
142830							→ Now well settled spectra back to 18k VIS 4k IR				
143100							→ Peltiers IC2 off (TEMP = +11°C)				
143140	GW P3 / Start R4	FL100	↑*	150	500	End P3 / Start R4	Spectra / Signal getting slightly 'low'				
143350		FL100	↑*	200	750	Start Dark View	(Temp +11°C)				
143407		FL100	↑*	200	750	Start Measurement					
144332	P4	FL100	ZENITH	200	750	START MEASUREMENT					
145340	P4	FL200	↑* ↓*	200	750	Change Zenith to NADIR at FL200 in prep for high level run (hopefully looking above Ci levels)					
145613				250	750	Start Dark Cal					
145640	P4	FL229	↓*	250	750	Start Measurement (* 6° TO AFT) (Looking NADIR now)					
150145			↑*	250	750	SWS now looking ZENITH.					
150217	P4	FL260	↑*	250	750	Recommence climb P4.					
150444						Camera H1 & Film ended (I)					
150554						Camera H1 & " started (II)					
150708	P4	FL299	↑*	250	750	Will continue to view SWS ZENITH as we climb to max alt (P4), then as we descend to under Ci (P5) then as we do SCL runs under Ci.					
			CONTEMPLATING WELL HERE.								
150900											
151144							→ Above Ci now. (~ FL320) (still cloudy)				
1514			↑*	250	750						
15	P4		↑*	300	1000	Change intg. Ldo cal views	SWS: (+12°C)				
151624	Turning		↑*	50	1000	Start Measurement; End of P4 at FL 340					

340
↓
250

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 143	Date	1/12/05	Operator(s)	DEL (U/T) & IDL	log page	5 of 6
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks	
				Vis	NIR		

151823	PS ↓	FL 340	↑ *	500 ms	1000 ms	Start R ↓ 340 to 250 (6° To Full) profiling back thro' Ci.	
152115			↑ *	←		Spectra peak ~ 20k counts vis.	
152350				←		Spectra peak ~ 30k vis.	
152530			↑ *	←		Spectra " ~ 40k vis	
152700		26.3kft		←		Controlling just about clipped now (Temp +12°C)	
1	End PS	25.0kft				End PS	
152850			↑ *	←		Start Dark Cal (Before next SCL run)	
152912			↑ *	500	1000	Start Measurement again now.	
153038	RS.1	FL 250	↑ *	500	1000	Start R at FL 250 (Under Ci)	
						Good spectra (VIS peak ~ 40k counts) on this run. (IR " ~ 10k ")	
153810					←	Spectra peak now ~ 20k on vis.	
153950					←	" " ~ 30k "	
154038	RS.1	FL 250	↑ *	500	1000	End RS.1. Turn back for next run for few minutes before orbit.	
154243	RS.2	FL 250	↑ *	500	1000	Start R6. (6° To Full) (Temp +12°C)	
154500						Spectra peak vis 20k → 30k on this run & for	
154825					←	Spectra peak 25k-30k	
155010	End RS.2	FL 250	↑ *	500	1000	End R6. Now descend to FL 240 to get under Ci. (Temp +13°C) Pelther	
155234						Start Dark Cal } With ALICES	
155258						Start Measurement } CAL	
155518		FL 240	↑ *	500	1000	Start RS orbit (Turn L) Heading 150° at start.	
155528		"	"	"	"	Hdg 110° re-established orbit No 1. (Temp +13°C)	

SWS FLIGHT LOG SHEET

Flight #	B 143	Date	1/12/05		Operator(s)	JRK (U/T) & JAL		log page	6 of 6	
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Mirr Pos	Int Times		Remarks				
				Vis	NIR					

155716			↑*			End Orbit . now 60°				
155742	Oct. I II	FL240	0.1sec	100	250	Start orbit 000° Orbit II				
			(SAMPLE PERIOD)			(orbit aborted) (CHANGE SAMPLE PERIOD)				
155848	Orbit III	FL240	0.1sec	100	100	Start 50° bank orbit Orbit III				
			(SAMPLE PERIOD)			(no change in Integ times)				
160018	End Ob	FL240	0.1	100	100	End orbit III (340°)				
160135		FL240	0.1sec	500	1000	Now return to larger integ times after orbits. (Temp +13°C)				
			Sample Period ↑*							
160444	PG ↑	FL240	↑*	500	1000	Profile P6 start. (*6° offset) FREE				
160550	PG	FL254	↑*	500	1000	Change Sample period → 1 sec. (SAMPLE PERIOD 1 sec) ——— now ———				
160810						Spectrum max = 10k (vis) now				
160920						← Contracting now				
161251						Dark View				
161314			↑*	1000	1000	Start Measurement				
161357						End P6 ↑				
161400	Start P7	FL320	↑*	1000	1000	Start P7 ↓ to FL290. (Temp +12°C)				
161550						← Contracting well now				
161650						Pelther → OFF. (Temp +11°C) (12)				
161732	End P7	FL290	↑*	1000	1000	End P7 (Sample period 1 sec)				
161943	Start P6	"	↑*	1000	1000	Start P6. SEL.				
162540						Max spectra (vis) ~ 70k - daylight now fading!				
162944	End P6	"	↑*	1000	1000	End P6. Turn (P)				
163209	Start P7	FL290	↑*	1000	1000	Start P8. Contrails gone?				
163715	End P7	FL250	"	"	"	End P8 Spectra v. small now.				
163743						Start Dark Current View				
163807			"	"	← "	Start Measurement, then shut-down				

163914 CAMERA TAPE II OFF

1 hr 33 min 00.

170254 →

LAND EXETER

(5hr 02).

(201)

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B** 143

Date: 1st December 2005

Instrument	Operated	Instrument	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>		<u>Cloud Physics</u>	
INU	Y	Probes	
XR5M GPS	Y	FFSSP	Y
Cruciform GPS	n	PCASP	Y
Satcom C	Y	2D-P	Y
Satcom H	Y	2D-C	Y
<u>Thermometers</u>		Cloudscope	N
De-Iced Temp	Y	SID 1	Y
Non De-Iced	Y	SID 2	N
Heimann	Y	HVPS	N
<u>Hygrometers</u>		CIP25	N
G. Eastern	Y	CIP100	Y
J. Williams	Y		
Nevzorov	Y		
TWC	Y		
FWVS	Y	Racks:	
<u>Radiometers</u>		INC	N
Upper Clear	Y	CCN / CPC	Y
“ Red	Y	CVI	N
“ Silicon	Y		
“ JO1D	N	<u>Aerosol</u>	
Lower Clear	Y	PSAP	N
“ Red	Y	Nephelometer	N
“ Silicon	Y	Filters	N
“ JO1D	N	AMS	N
<u>Large Radiometers</u>			
TAFTS	Y		
MARSS	Y		
DEIMOS	Y	<u>Others:</u>	
ARIES	y	NIR TDLAS	N
SWS	Y	2BT O3	N
<u>Chemistry</u>		VACC	N
Ozone	Y	PEROXIDE	N
SO2	Y	Formaldehyde	N
NOX	Y	ADA	Y
CO	y	CPI	Y
ORAC	N	NOxy	N
PAN	N	PTRMS	N
PERCA	N	Bag Sampling	N
WAS	N	Tube Sampling	N

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B143

Date: 1st December 2005

Instruments

1. ARINC interface problem – lost pressure data around 13.46 for approx 15 minutes
2. Camera demister causes mildly flickering video footage in ffc
3. [NON-CORE] TAFTS laser failed early in the flight – instrument u/s for flight.

Aircraft

Satcom H Calls

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B143:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	pre flight only, unmanned operation on auto calibrate so no In Flight log
CPI	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM
TAFTS	No log is ever taken for TAFTS
AVAPS (Dropsonde)	No sondes were launched so no log sheet required.

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

3 x Forward Facing Cameras
3 x Up/Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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